

Molecular docking studies of Meso-tartrate and Diiodophenylpyruvate enzymes

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Abstract- Oxidoreductases are enzymes that catalyze the oxidation of one molecule to another using NAD⁺ and NADP as co-factors. In this study, homology modeling and/or molecular docking are done for two selected homosapian enzymes Malate dehydrogenase (Uniprot ID: MDH1) and Homosapian alcohol dehydrogenase (1U3U). The homology modeling for Malate dehydrogenase was built in comparison with its porcine analog (5MDH) using SWISS-MODEL. Its active site was determined by aligning with the 5MDH template using PyMol. Homosapian alcohol dehydrogenase (1U3U) was selected as target crystal structure based on its specific criteria (resolution 1.60 Å, Rfree value 0.186, Ramachandran outliers value 0), and prepared with AutoDock. Its active site was determined using AutoDock grid tool. The co-crystallized ligand was prepared using open babel. Molecular docking was done for both enzymes, and five ligands from 89 ligands are the best results obtained based on their binding configuration and binding affinity using Autodock Vina.

Index Terms- human alcohol dehydrogenase, diiodophenylpyruvate reductase; homology modeling; protein-ligand docking; virtual screening, binding site prediction.

I.INTRODUCTION

Oxidoreductases are a class of enzymes that catalyze oxido-reduction reactions. Oxidoreductases can be oxidases or dehydrogenases. These enzymes are involved when molecular oxygen acts as an acceptor of hydrogen or electrons. Whereas, dehydrogenases are enzymes that oxidize a substrate by transferring hydrogen to an acceptor that is either NAD⁺/NADP⁺ or a flavin enzyme[1]. It plays an important role in both aerobic and anaerobic metabolism. They can be found in glycolysis, citric acid cycle (Kerbs cycle), oxidative phosphorylation, and in amino acid metabolism [2]. All enzymes that catalyse oxido-reductions are belong to EC 1. Oxidoreductases class. The substrate oxidized is regarded as a hydrogen or electron donor. The classification is based on 'donor: acceptor Oxidoreductase'. The common name is 'dehydrogenase', EC 1.1 subclass acting on the CH-OH group of donors. The common name is used wherever this is possible; as an alternative. 'Oxidase' is used only where O₂ is an acceptor. These dehydrogenases act on primary alcohols, secondary alcohols and hemi-acetals. Sub-subclasses are based on the acceptor: NAD⁺ or NADP⁺ (EC 1.1.1), a cytochrome (EC 1.1.2), oxygen (EC 1.1.3), a disulfide (EC 1.1.4), a quinone or similar compound (EC 1.1.5), or some other acceptor (EC 1.1.99)[3]. Malate dehydrogenases (MDH, L-malate:NAD, oxidoreductase, Diiodophenylpyruvate reductase, EC 1.1.1.37), catalyze the reversible NAD/NADH-dependent inter-conversion of the substrates malate and oxaloacetate. Two isoforms are found from this enzyme, mitochondrial isoform which is the key enzyme in the kerbs cycle that catalyzes the oxidation of malate. While the cytosolic (MDH1) isoform participates in the malate/aspartate shuttle across the mitochondrial membrane so that malate can pass through the membrane for further cellular processes. MDH1 is important in transporting NADH equivalents across the mitochondrial membrane, controlling tricarboxylic

acid (TCA) cycle pool size and providing contractile function. MDH1 has a strong tissue-specific distribution, being expressed primarily in cardiac and skeletal muscle and in the brain. While at intermediate levels in the spleen, kidney, intestine, liver, and testes, and at low levels in lung and bone marrow.

Alcohol dehydrogenases (ADH, Alcohol:NAD⁺ oxidoreductas , EC 1.1.1.1) are a group of zinc protein dehydrogenase enzymes that facilitate the interconversion between alcohols and aldehydes or ketones with the reduction of NAD⁺ to NADH. Alcohol dehydrogenase uses two molecular "tools" to perform its reaction, a zinc atom and a large NAD cofactor[4]. They also make important modifications to retinol, steroids, and fatty acids. The range of different types of alcohol dehydrogenase ensures that there will always be one that is perfect for the current task [5]. Alcohol dehydrogenase provides a line of defense against a common toxin in our environment.

Hence, the search for inhibitors of these enzyme to treat human diseases is a direct consequence of their significant physiological and toxicological roles. We need to identify the binding sites of these enzymes, fully automated docking-based virtual screening platform was developed by considering different protein conformations and the consensus docking strategy. In order to verify the reliability of the reported platform, a small database of about 10,000 compounds was filtered by using this method, and the top-ranked compounds were tested for their binding activity, orientation (or posing) within a targeted binding site[6].

In view of these challenges, docking is generally devised as a multi-step process in which each step introduces one or more additional degrees of complexity [7]. The process begins with the application of docking algorithms that POSE small molecules in the active site. Sampling these degrees of freedom must be performed with sufficient accuracy to identify the conformation that best matches the receptor structure, and must be fast enough to permit the evaluation of thousands of compounds in a given docking run. Algorithms are complemented by SCORING FUNCTIONS that are designed to predict the biological activity through the evaluation of interactions between compounds and potential targets [8]. In the absence of knowledge about the binding sites, cavity detection programs or online servers, can be utilized to identify putative active sites within proteins. The early elucidation for the ligand-receptor binding mechanism is the lock-and-key theory proposed by Fischer [14], in which the ligand fits into the receptor like lock and key. The earliest reported docking methods [15] were based on this theory and both the ligand and receptor were treated as rigid bodies accordingly. Then the "induced-fit" theory [16] created by Koshland takes the lock-and-key theory a step further, stating that the active site of the protein is continually reshaped by interactions with the ligands as the ligands interact with the protein. This theory suggests that the ligand and receptor should be treated as flexible during docking. Consequently, it could describe the binding events more accurately than the rigid treatment. In addition to problems associated with scoring of compound conformations, other complications exist that make it challenging to accurately predict binding conformations and compound activity. These include, among others, limited resolution of crystallographic targets, inherent flexibility, induced fit or other conformational changes that occur on binding, and the participation of water molecules in protein–ligand interactions. Without doubt, the docking process is scientifically complex.

II.MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is divided into five stages. In the first stage the two enzymes were selected, and at the end of this stage the homology modeling was applied for the Malate Dehydrogenase enzyme. In the second stage the two targets were prepared, and their co-crystallized ligand was determined. The ligands for virtual screening were prepared in the third stage. In fourth stage the two enzymes entered the molecular docking and virtual screening stage, finally the top five poses are selected and evaluated for each enzyme as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 work flow of this study

1. Selection of Proteins and homology model template

The structure of alcohol dehydrogenase protein of Homo sapiens (PDB ID: 1U3U) was retrieved from the protein data bank [15] in pdb format. “1U3U” structure was selected based on multiple criteria from its full report. It was found that 1U3U has a resolution of 1.60 Å which is a highly significant value (best resolution value lies between 1 Å and 3 Å), Rfree value equals 0.186 (Rfree value should be less than 0.2), and Ramachandran outliers value 0 which means 1U3U has no amino acids falls in the unfavorable region of the Ramachandran plot figure 1.

A novel NAD-dependent malate dehydrogenase enzyme has no available structure on PDB of Homo sapiens (Uniprot ID: MDH1) [16] was selected. The homology modeling method was selected for building the model using SWISS-MODEL [17], the best template (PDB ID: 5MDH) [18] was selected based on its identity score (95.50 %), Coverage (99 % GMQE) and the resolution (2.4 Å).

2. Preparation of target proteins

2.1 Preparation of Crystal structure

The alcohol dehydrogenase (1U3U) was visualized using the molecular graphics program PyMol intended for the structural visualization of proteins and was found in complex with N-Benzylformamide (BNF). Hydrogen atoms were added to the molecule prior molecular docking procedures. The active site of the protein was identified with reference to the co-crystallized ligand. The target and co-crystallized ligand were extracted and saved in PDB format. Open babel was used for preparing the co-crystallized ligand (Ligand.pdbqt) file, while the Target (Apo) was prepared in pdbqt format using AutoDockTools. In order to find active site position with right dimensions, the grid box of AutoDockTools was applied on both Ligand and Apo files.

2.2 Preparation of Homology structure

To detect the active site position, the created model was aligned with the 5MDH template using PyMol. Then the Target and Ligand files were prepared as mentioned in the previous paragraph.

3. Ligands preparation and selection

A ten random ligands were selected from zinc15 database [19] for tartrate dehydrogenase protein using its gene name (ADH1B) with other eighty-nine different ligands provided. Open babel was used for preparing them into pdbqt format.

4. Docking and virtual screening

The docking script uses these ten ligands in addition to the other provided eighty-nine ligands to find and select the best poses with the lowest energy by trying ten different poses for each ligand. The same process was applied for the homology mode. The 2D diagrams of the receptor ligand interaction for the top five ligands were obtained by Discovery studio.

For target-ligand docking analysis. Autodock Vina was used [20]. First, based on the already present co-crystallized ligand in the pdb file, the active site was defined with grid box parameters and coordinate of origin (x, y and z). This gives enough space to enhance ligand rotation and translation. The spacing between grid points was maintained at 1 angstrom. All ligands were docked to the active site of the protein. Throughout this study, the rotatable bonds of the ligands were set to be free, however the protein molecule was treated as rigid structure. A total of ten (21) docking runs were performed for each ligand with the number of modes set to 10 so as to achieve more accurate and reliable results. The five best results obtained based on the binding configuration and binding affinity were chosen for further analysis [22].

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation of Protein Structure

The human alcohol dehydrogenase enzyme (PDB ID: 1U3U) was evaluated based on multiple criteria (1.6 Å resolution, 0.186 Rfree, 0 ramachandran outliers). The ramachandran plot shows that 96.1 % of all residues were in favored (98 %) regions and 100.0 % of all residues were in allowed (>99.0 %) regions [23].

Figure 2: Ramachandran plot for the human alcohol dehydrogenase

Validation of Homology Model

The first validation of the template of malate dehydrogenase enzyme (PDB ID: 5MDH) was carried out using Ramachandran plot calculations computed with Molprobity program by checking the detailed residue-by-residue stereo-chemical quality of a protein structure. The ramachandran

plot shows that 92.9 % of all residues were in favored (98 %) regions and 98.8 % of all residues were in allowed (>99.0 %) regions. The results are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Ramachandran plot of the homology modeling template

To validate the results obtained using PyMol for aligning the model with the template, BLASTp was used for getting the identity of the two sequences [23]. The results in figure 4 shows that our model is very reliable as it has a high query cover value 100%, identity value 95% which is similar to the identity value obtained from SWISS-MODEL and E value equals 0 which is a significant value as shown in figure 4.

Max score	Total score	Query cover	E value	Ident	Accession
658	672	100%	0.0	95%	Query_99487

Figure 4: BLASTp results

Molecular Docking and Virtual Screening

The best docking score resulted from the virtual screening calculated using Autodock vina 4 shown table 1.

Alcohol Dehydrogenase	Docking Score	Malate Dehydrogenase	Docking Score
Cpds-mini48	-9.8	Cpds-mini20	-18.5
Cpds-mini23	-9.4	Cpds-mini11	-18.5
Cpds-mini27	-9.3	Cpds-mini35	-18
Cpds-mini17	-9.2	Cpds-mini13	-17.9
Cpds-mini15	-9.1	Cpds-mini24	-17.8

Table 1: Virtual screening results of the best fit ligands.

The Receptor-ligand interactions of human alcohol dehydrogenase (1U3U) and diiodophenylpyruvate reductase are shown in table 2 and table 3 respectively.

Ligands	No of hydrogen bonds	Hydrogen bonds interacting residues	Bond length (Å)	Residues involved in Hydrophobic interactions
Cpds-mini48	2	Arg369	6.19	-
		Val294	3.74	
Cpds-mini23	2	Pro295	4.73	-
		Ile269	5.06	
Cpds-mini27	2	Val200	4.4	-
		Thr178	4.07	
Cpds-mini17	1	Thr178	4.28	Val294
Cpds-mini15	1	Tyr319	5.92	Val318

Table 2: 1U3U Receptor-ligand interactions

Ligands	No of hydrogen bonds	Hydrogen bonds interacting residues	Bond length (Å)	Residues involved in Hydrophobic interactions
Cpds-mini20	2	Ser89 Asp42	4.34 4.07	Gln15
Cpds-mini11	3	Ser242 Arg92 Asn131	3.81 4.47 4.18	Ser241 Gly231 Val129 Gly130
Cpds-mini35	6	Arg162 Arg98 Arg92 Gln15 Ser89 Asn131	7.01 6.07 4.61 5.42 3.98 3.93	Ser241 Gly11 Gly130
Cpds-mini13	2	Asp42 Gln112	4.28 4.91	Asp42
Cpds-mini24	1	Gly11	3.9	Gly88 Gly11 Gln112

Table 3: Diiodophenylpyruvate Receptor-ligand interactions

number	Ligand	Affinity (Kcal/mol)	Ligand	Affinity (Kcal/mol)
1	co-ligand-nad	-20.5	-9.8	cpds-mini48
2	cpds-mini20	-18.5	-9.7	cpds-mini58
3	cpds-mini11	-18.5	-9.5	cpds-mini23
4	cpds-mini35	-18	-9.4	cpds-mini35
5	cpds-mini45	-18	-9.4	cpds-mini80
6	cpds-mini13	-17.9	-9.4	cpds-mini74
7	cpds-mini24	-17.8	-9.3	cpds-mini27
8	cpds-mini36	-17.7	-9.3	cpds-mini77
9	cpds-mini19	-17.7	-9.3	cpds-mini47
10	cpds-mini51	-17.6	-9.2	cpds-mini17
11	cpds-mini59	-17.6	-9.2	cpds-mini11
12	cpds-mini50	-17.5	-9.1	cpds-mini15
13	cpds-mini14	-17.5	-9	cpds-mini50
14	cpds-mini33	-17.4	-9	cpds-mini72
15	cpds-mini39	-17.4	-8.9	cpds-mini25
16	cpds-mini72	-17.4	-8.9	cpds-mini24
17	cpds-mini73	-17.4	-8.9	cpds-mini12
18	cpds-mini47	-17.4	-8.9	cpds-mini4
19	cpds-mini29	-17.3	-8.9	cpds-mini64
20	cpds-mini30	-17.3	-8.8	cpds-mini59
21	cpds-mini4	-17.3	-8.8	cpds-mini30
22	cpds-mini64	-17.3	-8.8	cpds-mini9
23	cpds-mini77	-17.3	-8.7	cpds-mini31
24	cpds-mini48	-17.3	-8.7	cpds-mini61
25	cpds-mini27	-17.2	-8.6	cpds-mini86
26	cpds-mini34	-17.1	-8.6	cpds-mini81
27	cpds-mini9	-17.1	-8.5	cpds-mini39
28	cpds-mini49	-17.1	-8.4	cpds-mini28
29	cpds-mini56	-17	-8.4	cpds-mini84
30	cpds-mini54	-17	-8.4	cpds-mini67
31	cpds-mini23	-17	-8.4	cpds-mini78
32	cpds-mini1	-17	-8.4	cpds-mini79
33	cpds-mini82	-17	-8.4	cpds-mini45
34	cpds-mini74	-16.9	-8.3	cpds-mini29
35	cpds-mini46	-16.8	-8.3	cpds-mini33
36	cpds-mini67	-16.7	-8.3	cpds-mini88
37	cpds-mini22	-16.6	-8.2	cpds-mini36
38	cpds-mini38	-16.6	-8.2	cpds-mini5
39	cpds-mini15	-16.6	-8.2	cpds-mini14
40	cpds-mini41	-16.6	-8.2	cpds-mini66
41	cpds-mini69	-16.5	-8.1	cpds-mini32

42	cpds-mini71	-16.5	-8.1	cpds-mini34
43	cpds-mini44	-16.5	-8.1	cpds-mini38
44	cpds-mini17	-16.4	-8.1	cpds-mini2
45	cpds-mini25	-16.3	-8	cpds-mini56
46	cpds-mini31	-16.3	-8	cpds-mini6
47	cpds-mini86	-16.3	-8	cpds-mini69
48	cpds-mini16	-16.3	-8	cpds-mini65
49	cpds-mini57	-16.2	-8	cpds-mini62
50	cpds-mini26	-16.2	-7.9	cpds-mini1
51	cpds-mini32	-16.2	-7.9	cpds-mini3
52	cpds-mini5	-16.2	-7.9	cpds-mini87
53	cpds-mini76	-16.2	-7.9	cpds-mini19
54	cpds-mini53	-16.1	-7.9	cpds-mini10
55	cpds-mini2	-16.1	-7.8	cpds-mini13
56	cpds-mini3	-16.1	-7.8	cpds-mini16
57	cpds-mini7	-16.1	-7.8	cpds-mini76
58	cpds-mini12	-16.1	-7.7	cpds-mini22
60	cpds-mini42	-16.1	-7.7	cpds-mini60
61	cpds-mini55	-16	-7.6	cpds-mini49
62	cpds-mini28	-16	-7.6	cpds-mini68
63	cpds-mini10	-16	-7.5	cpds-mini26
64	cpds-mini87	-15.9	-7.5	cpds-mini85
65	cpds-mini62	-15.8	-7.5	cpds-mini18
66	cpds-mini79	-15.8	-7.5	cpds-mini43
67	cpds-mini6	-15.7	-7.5	cpds-mini42
68	cpds-mini88	-15.7	-7.4	cpds-mini54
69	cpds-mini63	-15.7	-7.4	cpds-mini51
70	cpds-mini80	-15.6	-7.2	cpds-mini55
71	cpds-mini18	-15.6	-7.2	cpds-mini52
72	cpds-mini68	-15.5	-7.1	cpds-mini89
73	cpds-mini60	-15.5	-7.1	cpds-mini70
74	cpds-mini89	-15.4	-7.1	cpds-mini71
75	cpds-mini65	-15.4	-7	cpds-mini41
76	cpds-mini81	-15.3	-7	cpds-mini46
77	cpds-mini8	-15.2	-6.9	cpds-mini57
78	cpds-mini66	-15.2	-6.9	cpds-mini75
79	cpds-mini52	-15.1	-6.8	cpds-mini53
81	cpds-mini58	-15.1	-6.8	cpds-mini37
82	cpds-mini83	-15.1	-6.8	cpds-mini7
83	cpds-mini61	-15.1	-6.8	cpds-mini8
84	cpds-mini84	-15	-6.8	cpds-mini40
85	cpds-mini43	-14.9	-6.4	cpds-mini21
86	cpds-mini78	-14.8	-6.2	cpds-mini82
87	cpds-mini40	-14.5	-6.2	cpds-mini63
88	cpds-mini21	-14.4	-5.9	cpds-mini20

89	cpds-mini85	-14.3	-5.8	ligand2
90	cpds-mini37	-14.2	-5.6	co-ligand
91	cpds-mini75	-14	-5.6	ligand3
92	cpds-mini70	-12.5	-5.6	cpds-mini73
93	cpds-mini78	-14.8	-5.6	cpds-mini44
94	ligand2	-10.3	-5.2	ligand5
95	ligand4	-10	-5.1	ligand4
96	ligand3	-10	-5.1	ligand7
97	ligand7	-9.5	-4.9	ligand1
98	ligand5	-9.5	-4.6	cpds-mini83
99	ligand1	-8.9	-4.5	li
100	ligand10	-8.5	-4.5	ligand10
101	ligand6	-8.1	-4.1	l
102	ligand9	-7.1	-4.1	ligand6

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